

Table S1. Data file content accessibility of the information for the anthropometric measurements and questionnaire data.

Section	Content	Type of data: categories/ranges	Accessibility
Participant description	Participant ID: Participant ID for this study	Integer with unicity	Open
	Number: Number given to the participant during the data collection process	Integer with unicity	Restricted
	School: Visited school	Category data	Restricted
	Class: Class in which the participant was enrolled	Category data	Restricted
	Place of living: Place of residence according to school location	Category data: Rural; Urban	Restricted
	Sex: Sex of the participant	Category data: Female; Male	Open
	Age in months: Age in months of the participant	Numeric data: [166, 238]	Restricted
	Age in years: Age in years of the participant	Numeric data: [14, 20]	Restricted
	Age range: Age range of the participant	Ordinal category data: Between 14 and 15 inclusive; Between 16 and 17 inclusive; Greater than or equal to 18	Open
	Declared ethnic community: Declared cultural community obtained from questionnaire responses	Category data: Asian; European born in NC or Vanuatu; European born in France or elsewhere; Melanesian; Polynesian; Other	Restricted
Accelerometer information	ID.GENEActiv: Serial number of the device worn by the participant	Integer with 5 digits	Open
	Accelerometer starting day: Starting day of data collection, i.e. first day the device was worn	Date-time	Open
	Accelerometer day of removal: Day of device removal, i.e. last day the device was worn	Date-time	Open
	Accelerometer file: GENEActiv file associated with the participant and available in the Zenodo deposits	Text	Open
Anthropometric measurements and information	Tanner stage: Tanner stage declared by the participant describing sexual maturation	Ordinal category data: integer from 1 to 5	Restricted
	Waist size (in cm): Waist size of the participant in centimetres	Numeric data: [60, 106]	Restricted
Impedancemeter measurements	MACHINE to CHECKSUM: Collection of variables provided by the TANITA scale records described in the instruction manual [65].	Category, numeric and date-time data	Restricted
Weight status	IOTF L: IOTF Lambda index for computing the IOTF z-score	Numeric data	Restricted
	IOTF M: IOTF Mu index for computing the IOTF z-score		
	IOTF S: IOTF Sigma index for computing the IOTF z-score		
	IOTF z-score: IOTF z-score		
	IOTF percentile: IOTF percentile based on IOTF z-score		
	IOTF Weight status [45]: IOTF weight status based on IOTF z-score	Ordinal category data: underweight; normal; overweight; obese	Restricted
	IOTF WS: binary IOTF weight status based on IOTF Weight status	Ordinal category data: underweight or normal; overweight or obese	Open
	Cachera L: Cachera Lambda index for computing the Cachera z-score	Numeric data	Restricted
	Cachera M: Cachera Mu index for computing the Cachera z-score		
	Cachera S: Cachera Sigma index for computing the Cachera z-score		
	Cachera z-score: Cachera z-score		
	Cachera percentile: Cachera percentile based on Cachera percentile		
	Cachera Weight status [46]: Cachera weight status based on Cachera z-score	Ordinal category data: underweight; normal; overweight	Restricted
	Cachera WS: binary Cachera weight status based on Cachera Weight status	Ordinal category data: underweight or normal; overweight or obese	Open
	WHO L: WHO Lambda index for computing the WHO z-score	Numeric data	Restricted
WHO M: WHO Mu index for computing the WHO z-score			
WHO S: WHO Sigma index for computing the WHO z-score			
WHO z-score: WHO z-score			
WHO percentile: WHO percentile based on WHO z-score			
WHO Weight status [47]: WHO weight status based on WHO z-score	Ordinal category data: underweight; normal; overweight; obese	Restricted	
WHO WS: binary WHO weight status based on WHO Weight status	Ordinal category data: underweight or normal; overweight or obese	Open	
CDC L: CDC Lambda index for computing the CDC z-score	Numeric data	Restricted	
CDC M: CDC Mu index for computing the CDC z-score			
CDC S: CDC Sigma index for computing the CDC z-score			
CDC z-score: CDC z-score			
CDC percentile: CDC percentile based on CDC z-score			
CDC Weight status [48,49]: CDC weight status based on CDC z-score	Ordinal category data: underweight; normal; overweight; obese	Restricted	
CDC WS: binary CDC weight status based on CDC Weight status	Ordinal category data: underweight or normal; overweight or obese	Open	
HFZ BMI [50,51]: BMI-Healthy weight status computed with the FitnessGram reference	Ordinal category data: Very lean; Healthy fitness zone; Needs improvement; Needs improvement – Health risk	Restricted	
HFZ WS: Binary BMI-Healthy weight status computed with HFZ BMI	Ordinal category data: Very lean or Healthy fitness zone; Needs improvement or Needs improvement – Health risk	Open	
Food frequency questionnaire	Thirty-six questions about the participant food behaviour [31]	In most cases: category data from 5 to 7 options One question is numerical (integer from 0 to 12)	Open

		Two questions are free text	
Water at school	Five questions about the participant perception regarding water at school (cleanness, presence of chemicals, etc.)	Ordinal category data with 5 options	Open
Barriers and facilitators for physical activity	Nine questions for barriers and eleven questions for facilitators to engage in physical activity [32]	Ordinal category data with 5 options	Open
Sleep	Seven questions about sleep habits of the participant [33,34]	Category data from 7 to 19 options	Open
Sociodemographic *	Father's and mother's job Participant status at school (external, half border, internal) Presence of a garden or a field in the family where the participant lives	Free text data Category data	Restricted Open
Ethnic community membership	Six questions to measure the community membership [35]	Ordinal category data with 5 options	Open
New technologies and media	Thirty-six questions about the ownership of devices such as television, tablet, and smartphone as well as the connectiveness; participant behaviour regarding the use of screen devices and social media [36]	Category data and free text data	Open
Digital tools and health	Twenty-one questions about the use of media especially regarding health topics and healthy eating habits [28]	Category data and free text data	Open
Well-being	Five questions from the 5-item WHO well-being index [37]	Ordinal category data with 6 options	Open
Perception of health and weight	Two questions to assess how the participant perceives his/her own weight and health	Ordinal category data with 4 options	Open
Silhouette assessment and expectation	One scale question for the participant to assess his/her current weight status appearance and one scale question for the participant to express the weight status appearance he/she expects [38]	Integer data from 1 to 27	Open
Perception about biological sampling	Seven questions for the participant to express his/her opinion regarding a set of biological sampling	Ordinal category data with 5 options	Open

* Although the questionnaire tool contains a question about the birth date in this part, it is not included in the dataset because the age in months is include